

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOGOLLON****FIRST NAME: NESTOR****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 9%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What are the factors contributing to successful dissertation research?

- Good communication, good planning, effective process for writing, attention to detail, openness to serendipity.¹**
- Good planning, a good writing style, openness to serendipity, and literature review.
- Dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript.
- Good communication, effective writing process, attention to detail, and good planning skills.

2. What are the components of a dissertation abstract?

¹ James Sampson, 2017. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Second Edition). Florida State University, 13.

- Results, findings, problem statement, and methodology.
- Problem statement, research questions and hypotheses (if used), variable measures, procedures, findings, and implications.²**

3. What statements mention the correct use of the comma?

- Combine two sentences in one, divide adjectives not forming a series, and separate items in a series.
- To separate items in a series, link clauses, set off phrases and clauses, and separate adjectives in a series.³**
- Separate adjectives in a series, before, etc., and combine two sentences in one.
- Divide adjectives not forming a series to separate items in a series and always separate a main clause from the subordinate clause.

4. Which statements include the correct plural of these words: addendum, bacterium, consortium, genus, and medium?

- Addendums, bacteria, consortium, mediums, geneses.
- Addenda, bacteria, consortia, genera, media.⁴**
- Addendums, bacteria, consortiums, genera, mediums.
- Addenda, bacteriums, consortiums, genuses, media.

² Sampson, 26.

³ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Union Commission* (European Union, 2016, 2021), 8-10.

⁴ European Commission, 19.

5. What of the following statements define plagiarism?

- Plagiarism is when the writer credits the author for any graph, statistics, or visual borrowed from any source.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.⁵**
- Plagiarism is good academic writing practice.

Plagiarism is given credit to the author who produced the original work.

6. What is the correct format for author-date style citations?

- The author-date citations should include the author's last name, date, and relevant page numbers next to the reference in parenthesis.⁶**
- The Author-date citations should include the full name of the author and page numbers.
- The author-date citations should include the date, page, and the author name.
- The author-date citations do not have a specific format.

7. Define the components of the title of a dissertation.

- The title should indicate the variables and participants included in the research.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack Period 1*, Fourth Edition Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: Style for Students and Researchers, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 150.

The title should indicate the variables, participants, and setting for the research, as well as the treatment, variables, participants, and setting for the research.⁷

The title should include the setting of the research and the participants.

Depending on his objectives, the researcher decides what to include in the dissertation title.

8. According to Turabian, which statements describe guidelines for avoiding visual misrepresentations?

Do not make a table or figure unnecessarily complex or misleading simple; use complex tables and graphs implying false correlations.

Do not manipulate a scale to magnify or reduce a contrast; do not use a figure whose image distorts values; do not make a table or figure unnecessarily complex or misleadingly simple.⁸

Do not manipulate a scale to magnify or reduce contrast; use tridimensional and misleading simple graphs.

Do not make a table or figure unnecessarily complex or misleading simple; use tridimensional graphs; do not use a figure whose image distorts values.

9. What of these statements describe reasons to mention the source used in your research?

⁷ Sampson, 24.

⁸ Turabian, 102.

- There is no need to mention the sources as far as the writer paraphrases the words.
- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical; it is unfair to take someone's work and not give them credit; it is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.**⁹
- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical; the writer can choose to mention some sources and not others.
- It is unfair to take someone's work and not give them credit; only books and journals should be mentioned.

10. Using the Turabian note style, how do you cite a book with two authors?

- Author #1's First and Last Names, Title of the Book: Subtitle of Book, page number(s).
- Author # 1's First and Last Names, and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of the Book, and page number(s).

Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publications: Publisher's Name and Date of Publication), Page number(s).

- Author # 1's First and Last Name and Author #2's First and Last Names, Title of Book: Subtitle of Book (Place of Publication: Publisher's name, Date of Publication), Page number(s).**¹⁰

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

¹⁰ Turabian, 150.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.